

Chaotropic Ions and Acid Buffers as Eluents in Ligand Purification Using Semiautomated Affinity Chromatography

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A semiautomated technique using the principle of affinity chromatography has been developed for large scale purification of biospecific ligands. Among chaotropic ions and acid buffers as eluents, NaSCN proved to be a better eluting agent for CEA (carcino-embryonic antigen). The chaotropic ions (MgCl₂ and NaSCN), in general, were better eluents than acid buffers. The study was extended using biogel P-60, P-200 and P-300, as immunoadsorbents. Binding capacity of the three gels were in the ratio of 1.0 : 2.0 : 2.38. Use of P-300 as immunoadsorbent helped in the recovery of high affinity antibody.

ADVANCES in the field of immunology and immunochemistry¹ during the past two decades have necessitated an increasing need for purified ligands for detection or quantitation of biological substances in body fluids. Insoluble immunoadsorbent, utilizing the principle of affinity chromatography, serves as an elegant purification technique^{2,3}. It is based on the formation of an immune complex between ligand and receptor components formed by covalently linking proteins to each other or to insoluble supports such as agar or sephadex gel. After the formation of the complex, the gel is washed free of uncoupled proteins. Thereafter, the complex is dissociated yielding the desired substances in a highly purified state. This principle has been used by various workers^{4,5} utilizing techniques like column or batch for ligand purification. Both of these techniques are cumbersome and time-consuming whenever a sizable quantity of purified ligand is needed. This report describes an effort to semi-automate the batch technique and the experience with the apparatus using different types of immunoadsorbents, ligands and ligand-dissociating fluids.

Apparatus :

1. Amicon Company pressure dialysis units, Models No. 402 and 12 :

Amicon Model No. 12 was used for processing small amounts of immunoadsorbent (about 1.5-2.0 g), whereas Model No. 402 was used for larger quantities (about 75-100 g). The molecular membranes in the latter units were replaced by nylon polyester cloth (pore size 400×400 which allowed fluids to escape while retaining the immunoadsorbents). Positive pressure (2-5 pounds/in²) from a nitrogen tank was used to rapidly evacuate the fluids from the unit's chambers.

2. Home made elution unit :

The chambers of the units are constructed of tubular acrylic plastic measuring 10.5 cm in length and 7.5 cm in outside diameters. The walls measure 0.5 cm in thickness. Both ends are threaded for a

Fig. 1. Exploded view of the elution chamber.

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distance of 1.5 cm. The ends are closed by threaded end pieces (cap and base) measuring 9 cm in diameter and 3 cm in depth, each of which contains an O-ring measuring 7.5 cm in diameter. The base is fitted with a porous filter support disc which, in turn, is covered with a nylon filter cloth secured in position by an O-ring. A discharge tube measuring 2×0.5 cm (to drain the chamber) is included in the base as shown in Fig. 1.

A 2.6 cm hole to accommodate a No. 4 rubber stopper is drilled through the cap 2 cm from one edge. A teflon rod measuring 18 cm in length and 1 cm in diameter is suspended from the midportion of the upper cap by two tightly fitted grommets recessed in the inner and outer surfaces of the cap, respectively. A swivel, inserted into the lower end of the teflon rod, in turn, is fitted with a teflon-coated magnetic stirring bar measuring 5.4×1 cm. Although airtight, the teflon rod may be raised or lowered.

The rubber stopper is inserted from the inside of the cap to prevent its displacement under pressure. A plastic Y-tube (size 5/16") contained in the stopper allows the latter to be displaced, but prevents it from falling into the chamber. One end (of the two external openings) in the Y-tube is connected to a two-part plastic connector; the wall of the outer portion of the connector is closed by fusing the edges with a flame. The other end of the Y-tube is connected to a common supply tube (C).

Fig. 2. Semiautomated batch elution from affinity type immunoabsorbent.

Four such elution units are normally positioned on multi-magnetic stirrer platform (Fig. 2); their respective discharge tubes are connected below to a closed, common plastic drainage tube (H) filled with a spout at one end. The tube (3.0×3.5 cm) is held at an angle of 15° to the table top by two feet, unequal in heights, measuring respectively 4 and 2 cm. Each of the elution units is connected above to the common supply tube (C) by plastic tubing (fitted with clamps).

The common supply tube containing four entry portals (labeled 1,2,3 and 4 in Fig. 2) is connected to a supply of saline, buffer No. 1, buffer No. 2 or chaotropic solution and to a nitrogen tank, respectively. Inserted between the buffer supply No. 1 and No. 2 are two disposable 100 ml plastic burettes. Clamps are attached to the tubing leading from the saline, buffers, chaotropic solution and N₂ tank supplies. The apparatus between the salines and the elutions units are attached to a wooden back-board which can be tilted to completely empty the common supply tube when necessary. Operation of this home-made unit is essentially similar to the commercial units.

Materials and reagents :

Immunosorbents : Protein co-polymer, Sephrose and Biogel P-300, each containing a complexed monospecific antibody or antigen.

Phosphate buffer saline (PBS),

Glycine-HCl 0.1 M pH 2.5,

Chaotropic ionic solution (3 M MgCl₂ and 3 M NaSCN),

Urine containing kappa L-chains obtained from patient with kappa-type myeloma, lyophilized and stored at room temperature until the kappa L-chains were purified,

Carcinoembryonic antigen was purified from a case of colonic carcinoma.

Experimental

Radiolabeled studies (preliminary experiments) : To avoid contamination of the apparatus by radioactive materials, the following preliminary experiments were carried out with radio-labeled materials in test tubes :

- 1) Capacity studies of different type gels (P-60, P-200, P-300).
- 2) Elution studies using acid buffer at different pHs.
- 3) Elution studies using chaotropic ions.

Non radio-labeled studies : These studies were carried out using the apparatus as described earlier.

- a) Purification of kappa L-chains.

Preparation of immunoabsorbents :

Goat anti-human IgG and rabbit anti-CEA antibody (γ-fractions) respectively were covalently

bonded to Biogel P-60 (100-200 mesh), P-200 (100-200 mesh) and P-300 (-400 mesh) as directed by Avrameas and Ternyck⁶ by first activating the gels by using 6% solution of glutaraldehyde in 0.1M phosphate buffer adjusted to pH 7.0. Thirty (30) mg of the antiserum was mixed with 10 ml of centrifuged and activated beads for sensitization.

Simultaneously 10 mg of γ -fractions of anti-IgG antibody and anti-CEA antibody were covalently bonded to 1 g of CNBr-activated Sephrose 4B as directed by Pharmacia⁷.

Preparation of antisera :

Antisera were produced in rabbits against kappa L-chains and carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) as previously described⁸. The antisera were absorbed by insolubilized serum proteins, and in the case of anti-CEA, by insolubilized extracts of normal colon until they were monospecific. Their IgG fractions were then isolated as described earlier¹.

Preparation of radio-labeled antigen :

One hundred (100) mg of chromatographically purified human IgG in 50 ml of 0.2 M phosphate buffer pH 7.2 was mixed with 10 ml of Na¹²⁵I (1 mCi) and 25 ml of enzymobead and the reaction was allowed to proceed for 20 min at room temp using 1% beta D-glucose as suggested by Biorad⁶. ¹²⁵I tagged protein was separated from unattached ¹²⁵I by gel filtration in Sephadex G-50. ¹²⁵I-CEA was obtained from a commercial source (Hoffman-La Roche, Nutley, N. J. 07110).

Saturation of immunoabsorbents with radiotagged ligands (IgG and CEA) :

Radiolabeled antigens were incubated with their homologous immunoabsorbents monospecific for IgG and CEA, respectively. The incubations were allowed to continue overnight following which the gels were thoroughly washed with PBS. The radiolabeled ligands were then eluted with 0.1M acetate buffer pH 4.0 and 0.1M glycine-HCl buffers pH 3.5 to 1.4 and with chaotropic ionic solutions (3M MgCl₂ and 3M NaSCN).

Binding capacity of polyacrylamide gels :

Equal amounts of Biogel P-60, P-200 and P-300 were saturated with an excess of ¹²⁵I-IgG (11.5 mg). After overnight incubation, the gels were thoroughly washed, the radioactivity counted and the amount of protein associated with each gel was determined. Controls (unsensitized gels) were to react with equal amounts of labeled proteins under identical conditions and the nonspecific attached radioactivity was then to be determined.

Elution procedure :

In the preliminary experiment, equal amounts of complexed immunoabsorbents (Biogel and Sephrose 4B) were taken in different tubes coated with BSA, and mixed with equal volume of various ligand dissociating fluids at room temp. At a regular interval extending from 30 min to 92 hr, the tubes were centrifuged and radioactivity of an aliquot counted following which the beads were resuspended. Results are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

The purification procedure was further extended using affinity chromatography. According to their binding capacities, amounts of P-60, P-200 and P-300 complexed immunoabsorbents containing equal amount of attached antigen were equilibrated in different columns and washed thoroughly with PBS till the washings were very near the background counts. Antigen (¹²⁵I-CEA) was eluted with 3M NaSCN and the eluates counted.

Use of semi-automated technique was also made to study the purification of a protein on a mass scale. In one set, polymerized normal human serum was complexed with goat anti-human and a homologous purified antiserum was eluted by 3M MgCl₂. In another set, human kappa light chain was isolated from anti-kappa chain immunoabsorbent and kappa chain lyophilized urine using 0.1M glycine-HCl pH 2.4 as the elution fluid.

Recovery of kappa L-chains :

Lyophilized urine containing kappa L-chains (78.6 mg) was incubated with 40 ml of P-300 sensi-

TABLE I—ELUTION OF IgG (%) USING BATCH TECHNIQUE

Elution system	Time													
	30 min		60 min		120 min		180 min		20 hr		44 hr		68 hr	
	P-300	Seph 4B	P-300	Seph 4B	P-300	Seph 4B	P-300	Seph 4B	P-300	Seph 4B	P-300	Seph 4B	P-300	Seph 4B
0.1 M acetate pH 4.0	-	-	0.5	0.0	0.9	0.0	0.5	0.0	1.2	0.4	3.5	0.2	-	0.6
0.1 M Gly-HCl pH 3.5	-	-	7.7	10.6	10.5	9.6	12.3	9.7	27.9	13.0	42.9	23.6	-	33.3
0.1 M Gly-HCl pH 3.0	-	-	15.6	40.2	24.1	28.5	25.2	35.2	35.2	23.7	46.3	24.3	-	20.5
0.1 M Gly-HCl pH 2.5	-	-	33.8	56.8	41.1	53.6	49.8	53.1	59.2	45.4	64.3	45.4	-	43.8
0.1 M Gly-HCl pH 2.0	-	-	47.5	57.3	52.6	56.8	53.5	54.1	59.3	53.8	55.8	53.7	-	51.0
0.1 M NaCl-HCl pH 1.4	-	-	55.2	61.6	54.3	51.0	54.6	48.1	56.0	50.0	59.9	36.9	-	32.7
3 M MgCl ₂	-	-	19.2	74.9	25.6	72.0	37.4	48.1	37.7	50.0	52.8	82.4	-	80.0
3 M NaSCN	-	66.5	22.0	77.8	29.9	84.0	29.2	76.2	42.3	88.0	51.1	-	-	-
		70.7						85.0		91.2				

TABLE 2—ELUTION OF CEA (%) USING BATCH TECHNIQUE

Elution system	Time															
	30 min		60 min		120 min		240 min		20 hr		44 hr		68 hr		92 hr	
	P-300	Seph 4B	P-300	Seph 4B	P-300	Seph 4B	P-300	Seph 4B	P-300	Seph 4B	P-300	Seph 4B	P-300	Seph 4B	P-300	Seph 4B
0.1 M acetate pH 4.0	1.0	—	1.0	0.1	7.3	1.0	6.8	1.9	10.5	3.3	35.0	—	32.4	—	32.5	—
0.1 M Gly-HCl pH 3.5	2.4	—	2.4	5.1	4.0	7.0	3.8	8.1	18.2	11.9	37.5	—	25.3	—	28.8	—
0.1 M Gly-HCl pH 3.0	7.2	—	8.3	16.0	21.3	18.5	22.8	20.6	43.1	24.4	55.6	—	49.5	—	53.4	—
0.1 M Gly-HCl pH 2.5	11.6	—	16.0	39.5	33.5	41.6	37.1	43.4	53.8	48.2	52.1	—	47.1	—	47.1	—
0.1 M Gly-HCl pH 2.0	22.7	—	26.5	54.8	28.0	57.4	39.3	56.8	40.8	61.2	57.4	—	58.1	—	58.1	—
0.1 M NaCl-HCl pH 1.4	30.7	—	30.6	84.1	38.1	83.8	38.9	85.9	59.1	89.8	58.3	—	64.2	—	61.2	—
3 M MgCl ₂	2.0	—	6.4	41.6	17.1	50.8	26.1	58.1	41.9	82.2	55.5	—	54.3	—	63.5	—
3 M NaSCN	4.8	—	20.9	53.7	28.7	63.1	39.6	71.4	50.0	99.0	72.4	—	82.7	—	84.7	—

tized with radio-tagged homologous antibody. The unbound protein in the supernatant was then determined. The immunoabsorbent was exhaustively washed until no further protein could be determined in the wash fluid at 280 nm. The immunoabsorbent was then transferred to the chamber of the apparatus and washed several times with 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH 7.0 followed by successive aliquots of 50 ml of 0.1 M glycine-HCl buffer pH 3.5 to elute attached proteins. The latter step was repeated until the O.D. was less than 0.5 at 280 nm (12 elutions).

Purification of CEA :

58.2 mg of gamma fraction of homologous anti-CEA antiserum incorporated in biogel P-300 immunoabsorbent was incubated overnight at 45° with perchloric acid extract of colonic adenocarcinomatous tissue. Following incubation, the gel was thoroughly washed with 0.1 M ammonium acetate pH 6.25 and two washes of PBS. CEA was eluted with acid buffers and chaotropic ions.

Results

With a little practice the apparatus proved to be simple to operate. The amount of ligand recovered depended on a variety of factors, viz, amount immunoabsorbent used, avidity of the antiserum, length of incubation period of the ligand with the immunoabsorbent, etc. Contamination of eluted ligand by extraneous proteins varied from a total absence to moderate depending on a number of factors, chief of which was the duration and effectiveness of the saline washing cycle. When the optical density at 280 nm of the wash fluid approached zero, contamination was usually negligible but not invariably so.

It proved to be expedient to follow the saline wash with an acidic wash which at times eliminated contaminants released by the more acidic eluting fluid. When a protein copolymer was used as the immunoabsorbent, albumin and prealbumin in small quantities were continuously leached into the ligand eluting fluid so that it had to be removed by Sephadex gel chromatography.

The chief advantage of the apparatus described here lies in the ability of the operator to rapidly carry out sequential steps in the attachment, washing and elution of the ligand *in situ*, repeating the cycle as often as necessary to obtain the desired amount of ligand. The concentration of the ligand in the solution is immaterial since the latter binds to the immunoabsorbent, with the result that very dilute solutions can readily be used to saturate the polymer.

For large scale purification of a ligand, it is necessary to optimize the elution conditions. Results on the purification of IgG and CEA using acid buffers and chaotropic ions have been recorded in Tables 1 and 2. The numbers represent the percent of the total ligand initially bound to the immunoabsorbent.

Dissociation using acid buffers :

0.1 M acetate pH 4.0 and 0.1 M glycine-HCl pH 1.4 to 3.5 were used as the dissociating fluids. Recovery of IgG (Table 1) was 33.8% when pH 2.5 buffer was incubated for 1 hr with P-300 immunoabsorbent. Under similar conditions, Sephrose 4B gel yielded 56.8%. Increase in the incubation time did not increase the yield but a lower pH increased the recovery as expected. Recovery from Sephrose 4B immunoabsorbent, in general, was greater than from P-300 as is evident from Tables 1 and 2. Results on the recovery of CEA (Table 2) were similar to that of IgG.

Dissociation using chaotropic ions :

Tables 1 and 2 delineate the use of 3 M MgCl₂ and 3 M NaSCN as eluents for human IgG and CEA. Sephrose 4B immunoabsorbent, in contact with the chaotropic ions for 3 hr, released 76.2 to 85% of the ligand (IgG), whereas under similar conditions P-300 complex yielded around 37%. Sephrose 4B complex, when incubated for 1 hr with either of the ions, yielded over 74%, whereas the recovery from P-300 complex was only around 22%. Recovery of CEA was similar to that of IgG. It is, however, interest-

ing to note that sodium thiocyanate recovered more CEA than $MgCl_2$.

Recovery using semi-automated affinity chromatography :

Results of previous experiments (Tables 1 and 2) helped set-up the final recovery experiments using semi-automated affinity technique. Table 3 presents two sets of data where 30 g and 50 g of immunoadsorbents were incubated with 10 ml of solution containing human antibody. Acid buffer pH 2.0 recovered 204 mg/ml of the ligand whereas with $MgCl_2$, the yield was 370.1. Sequential recoveries using different acid buffers and varying concentration of $MgCl_2$ are also recorded in Table 3. Purity of the antibody was checked by radial immunodiffusion (RID) and immunoelectrophoresis (IEP).

TABLE 3—ELUTION OF ANTIHUMAN ANTIBODY USING SEMIAUTOMATED TECHNIQUE

Elution system	Kappa light chain		Antihuman antibody (mg/ml)	
	+	++	Immunosorbent : 30 g	Immunosorbent : 50 g
Glycine-HCl (0.1 M, pH 3.0)	+		97.8	120.0
Glycine-HCl (0.1 M, pH 2.5)	++		163.2	204.3
Glycine-HCl (0.1 M, pH 2.0)	++		294.0	217.5
$MgCl_2$ (1.0 M)	+		102.2	127.5
$MgCl_2$ (2.0 M)	++		125.3	156.3
$MgCl_2$ (3.0 M)	+++		370.1	462.5

CEA and kappa light chains were also purified in similar manner. Recovery of CEA was 22.5 mg/ml

and that of kappa light chain 16. mg/ml. In another experiment, human IgG was purified using DEAE Sephadex. 50 ml of normal human serum yielded 10 mg of the immunoglobulin. Purity of these proteins were also confirmed by RID and IEP.

Binding capacity of polyacrylamide gels :

Table 4 records the binding capacity of Biogel P-60, P-200 and P-300, where gamma globulin was covalently attached to the gel matrix using glutaraldehyde. Results have also been represented graphically in Fig. 3. In successive experiments where IgG (gamma globulin) was covalently bonded to P-60,

TABLE 4—BINDING CAPACITY OF POLYACRYLAMIDE GEL TO GAMMA GLOBULINS

Gel	Wet weight of gel (g)	Gamma globulin (mg)	Gamma globulin attached (mg)*	Binding capacity
				P-60 : P-200 : P-300
P-60	2.8	11.52	1.61	1 : 2 : 2.38
P-200	3.0	11.52	3.23	
P-300	2.3	11.52	3.83	

* per wet weight (g) of gel.

P-200 and P-300, 4.0 mg of the protein could not saturate either of the gels (2.8 g of P-60, 3.0 g of P-200 and 2.3 g of P-300), 8.0 mg of IgG could saturate only P-60, whereas 11.5 mg of IgG saturated all the three gels. Capacity of the gels when calculated in terms of IgG/g was found to be in the ratio of 1 : 2 : 2.38 (Table 4) for P-60, P-200 and P-300, respectively. The capacity experiment aided in the establishment of three different affinity columns using P-60, P-200 and P-300 gels containing the same amount of antigen. On elution with 3 M NaSCN, 49.6% and 40.0% of the antibody was isolated in

Fig. 3. Recovery of CEA with P-60, P-200 and P-300 immunoaffinity columns.

void volumes of P-60 and P-200, whereas only 24.5% was isolated in the void volume of P-300 and 27% in the later fractions (Fig. 3).

Comments and Conclusion

That the affinity type of adsorption and desorption applied to insolubilized immunoadsorbents is revolutionizing the purification of biospecific substances is attested to by the rapidly burgeoning mass of literature on the subject. Although the initial enthusiasm for this technique has been dampened somewhat by the realization that a number of shortcomings are inherent in the technique, particularly non-specific adsorption of contaminants, the deficiencies have been offset by expansion of the approach to different types of specimens. Because of the general utilitarianism and widespread use of affinity procedures, development of more rapid, semi-automated and automated techniques to reduce the expenditure of work and time associated with the procedure is of practical importance. The simple apparatus described in this communication provides the opportunity to effectively speed up the purification of substances on a preparative scale. With respect to the type of immunoadsorbent used, simple precipitation of the gamma fraction of a monospecific antiserum by 10% polyethylene glycol (PEG) followed by polymerization with glutaraldehyde provides a rapid, simple procedure for preparing efficient immunoadsorbents which are often preferable and more economical than commercially supplied pre-sensitized gels. Also, less complete but more frequent elution of a substance coupled to a ligand are more efficient than prolonged elution⁶. Our results have shown that ten to twenty elutions are required to release the major portion of a bound substance from its ligand. Finally, it is pertinent to point out that the apparatus may be used to advantage for purifying substances by the ion-exchange principle as described for IgG.

Although there is little doubt that sophisticated, automated equipment and techniques will be developed in the near future to deal with the purification of substances by the affinity principle, the simple approach described above is immediately available

for use. Recovery results of all the elutions have been reported in Tables 1, 2, 3 and Fig. 3. As expected, recovery is higher at a lower pH but it is also evident that chaotropic ions ($MgCl_2$, NaSCN) dissolve and dissociate antigen-antibody complexes. Dissociation of complexes with $MgCl_2$, NaSCN occurs rapidly in contrast with acid dissociation, for which contact times of several hr are needed for a significant recovery. The protein immunospecifically purified by the chaotropic ions retained its ability to combine with ligand to form soluble and insoluble complexes. In 3M NaSCN and 3M $MgCl_2$, the concentration used for protein purification, no significant amount of irreversible gross structural changes was noted in any of the proteins. Saussure and Dandliker¹⁰ observed that at 4.5 M and above, SCN caused changes in the sedimentation behaviour of gamma globulin, antigen and complexes. These changes were reversible by dialysis.

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